

THE ORAL VOWEL SYSTEM OF PAKISTANI LANGUAGES: A CASE STUDY OF TYPOLOGY

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15400987>

Keywords

Pakistani, language, universal, common and uncommon vowels

Article History

Received on 06 April 2025

Accepted on 06 May 2025

Published on 14 May 2025

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Abstract

The study of universal tendencies in the languages of the world is the linchpin of any investigation to phonetics. This study is a linguistic typological study which means its concerns are categorizing languages on the basis of their common and uncommon features. The focus of current study is to find out the most common and uncommon oral vowels in Pakistani languages and make their feature hierarchy for better understandings of oral vowels system in Pakistani languages. The vowels of fifteen Pakistani languages are investigated and listed categorically in this study. Hence it gives a comprehensive overview of oral vowel system of languages spoken in different areas of Pakistan. In the end, the universal statements are devised after a thorough observation of the language types which are applicable on these fifteen Pakistani languages.

INTRODUCTION

Pakistan is a multilingual country. It is situated in the southern part of the Asia. Almost seventy languages are spoken in Pakistan (Rahman, 2010, p.39). Urdu is the national language and it is also the Interlanguage of Pakistan. The major languages of Pakistan are Urdu, Punjabi, Sindhi, Balochi, Siraiki, Pashto etc. A brief introduction of some major languages on which the study is focusing are the following.

Northwestern group

Urdu

Urdu is the second most commonly used language in the world (Rahman, 2010). It is the Lingua franca and the language of unity and solidarity in Pakistan. It is spoken almost in all parts of Pakistan and is most widely understood language in the country. The Urdu language belongs to Indo-Aryan family.

Punjabi

Punjabi is a widely spoken language in Pakistan and it contains a larger ethnic identity with it. According to the Census 2008 of Pakistan, number of Punjabi Speakers in Pakistan is 76,335,300, which is approximately 75% of Pakistan's total population (Sara and Katy, 2009). Still Punjabi is neither an official language nor a medium of instruction in education. Punjabi is an Indo-Aryan language.

Hindku

Hindko is culturally focused and geographically centered in the areas of Khyber-Pukhtunkhwa province. Hindko, Siraiki, Punjabi and Pohtohari are quite related languages. It is basically spoken in the districts Abbottabad, Peshawar, Mansehra and Kohat (Radloff & Dyrud 2011).

Saraiki

Siraiki is an Indo-Aryan language and a widely spoken language in the Southern Punjab. It is spoken in the areas of Multan, Muzaffargarh, Dera ghazi khan and the surrounding belt. There have been much political issues and Siraiki people have been fighting for the protection of their ethnic identity (Radloff & Dyrud, 2011).

Pahari

Pahari language is spoken in the Murree which is tehsil of Rawalpindi. A slightly different dialect of Pahari is also spoken in the Azad Kashmir. Pahari language changes into Hindko when we move from Ayubia to Niathiagali (Lothers, 2010). Pahari is an Indo-Aryan language.

Iranian Group

East Iranian

Pushto

Pashto is a major language and is spoken in many areas of the Pakistan. It is a major language in KPK and Baluchistan province. Its speakers are also found in Punjab and in the Federal area. It is spoken in the districts of Peshawar, Hazara, Banu, Kohat and Dera Ismail khan (Hallberg, 1992).

Ormuri

Ormuri is a dialect of Waziri Pashto spoken in Waziristan. The Burki people of Kangiruram in South Waziristan is the base of Ormuri speakers. Baraki Barak in Loghar, Afghanistan also has Ormuri speakers approximately 6000 in numbers. Ormuri language belongs to the Indo-Iranian language group. The very small number of native speakers of Ormuri language makes it an endangered language that is considered to be in a "threatened" state (Ethnologue 2017).

Wakhi

Wakhi is an East-Iranian language. Wakhi is spoken in four northern valleys of Pakistan, i.e. Hunza, Iskhoman, Yasin and Yarkhun. The number of its speakers is less but still there are quite documental and literary work are being done to preserve this language (Backstrom, 1992).

West Iranian

Hazara Persian

Persian is spoken by the people of Hazara tribe. This tribe is in the Baluchistan. Hazara Persian is also called Hazargi. This tribe has not forgotten their mother tongue although there are some major language in the neighbor like Urdu, Balochi and Pashto (Muhammad Owtadoiajam, 1976). Hazara people have also mutual intelligibility with the Persian of Iran.

Balochi

Balochi is spoken in South Western Pakistan, in the province of Balochistan as well as by the smaller population in Punjab and Sindh and by a larger ratio of speakers in Karachi (Jahani & Korn, 2009). Balochi language belongs to the West-Iranian group and is prominent Iranian language.

Dardic Group

Shina

Shina language belong to Dardic sub-group of the Indo-Aryan Languages family mostly used by Shiina people as their native language in all parts of Gilgit Baltistan, Pakitan, in Northern Areas of Pakistan. According to (Ethnologue 2017) "The Dialects of Shina language are Gilgiti (the prestigious and standard dialect), Chelasi Kohestani, Asturi, Drasi, Guraizi, Jalkuti, Kolaii, and Palasi. Other languages used by Shina people are Brokaskat (also called as the Shina of Baltistan and Drass), Domaa, Kohistani Shina, Phalula, Savi, and Ushojo. The Language Shina is the language of nearly 40% population of Gilgit Baltistan. The areas in which this language is spoken includes Southern Hunza Astore, Dareel, Chilas, Tangiir, Gilgit, Ghizer, Guraiz, Drass, Juglot Valley, Drotte Palas, Kolai, and Kohistan with 500000 native speakers".

Khovar

Khovar is the koine of District Chitral of Khyber Pukhtukhwa. Khovar is the most widely spoken language of Torkhow, Mulkhov, Laspur and Yarkhun valleys. Khovar is also spoken in the villages of Yasin and Sandhi in the Yasin valley (Decker, 1992).

Palula

Palula is language of nearly 10000 speakers residing in Asherate and Brir valley in district Chitral, fraction of the population in village Kalkatak, most people in village Purigal in Shishikoh valley in Chitral District Speaks Palula. Sau villege in Afghanistan, and Khalkot village in Dir Ditriect in Pakistan also has a very close varity of Palula language speakers (Ethnologue 2017).

Tibetic Group

Balti

Balti is the only Tibetic language spoken in Pakistan. It is commonly used by people of Skardu, Rondu, Shigar, Khapalu and Kharmang. These are the villages in Baltistan. Balti has a close relation with Ladhaki, spoken in the adjacent districts of Kashmir held by Indian Territory. These districts are quite close to the Baltistan (Backstorm, 1992).

Language Isolate

Brushuski

Burushaski is the language of Hunza valley. It is also spoken in the Nagar and Yasin Valley It is an isolated language. Burushaski is being spoken by almost fifty to eighty thousand people (Anderson, 2007).

Linguistic typology

“The lingual explanation of typology has to do with the classification of structural types across languages of the world” (Croft, 1989). The Linguistic typology shows a quite obvious structural differences and similarities between the languages. It can be regarded as the classification of languages on the basis of their structural properties. One important thing about linguistic typology is that the type of languages in the typology is not based on the genetic categorization of languages. A single type can include any language from any family. The genetic resemblance can be found between the languages but it is not always there. From these points it is clear that linguistic typology does not concern with a single language but a pile of languages. A linguistic typology is the structural variations across the languages. These variations can be in Phonology, Morphology, Syntax, Semantics etc. So the linguistic typology is the categorization of different languages into different types in different domains and in different aspects within those domains. It is clear that linguistic typology is not

about the types of languages on the basis of their genetic relatedness rather it is systematic structural classification of languages. For example “if a language has nasal vowels then these nasal vowels will always be less in numbers as compare to the Oral vowels in that language” (Finegan, 2005). This universal is applicable for all the languages in the world. This would contain all the languages that have this structural characteristic. Feature hierarchy is an important tool involved in the linguistic typology. This hierarchy shows the features which are common and uncommon in a language. If a feature is unmarked then it is more common and if a feature is more marked then it would be less common. Feature hierarchy moves from left to right from unmarked to marked (Croft, 1989).

Language universals

Languages universals are the universal statements about the languages. These universals are for all the languages. The language universals are the principles on which the languages can be categorized on their structural characteristic. Thus language universals are not made for a single or a group of languages but for all the languages. Language universals also represent the cognitive ability of a speaker. The Homo sapiens have developed not a singular language that is verbalized and comprehended but there are more than 6000 different languages in the world each of which is individually complicated and clued-up (Finegan, 2008). Universal principle is a key concept towards the formation of any particular language typology. For example there is a universal statement that all languages of the world would must have first and second person pronoun. This is a universal statement which has been made while keeping in focus all the languages of world. “Linguists must practice caution while devising a universal statement” (Finegan, 2008). As Linguistic typologies are not bound to the genetic relationship between the languages. So language universals are for all the languages from any language family. These language universals are the choices made by the speakers according to their social and cognitive ability.

Language universals are of the following types.

- i) Absolute Non-Implicational Universals
- ii) Absolute Implicational Universals

iii) Non-Implicational Tendencies

iv) Implicational Tendencies

If a universal is conditioned then it will be an implicational one. For example if there are nasal vowels in a language then it must have oral vowels. A non-implicational universal would not have any condition, e.g. all the languages have oral vowels. A tendency is not applicable to all the languages but it is a possibility found in most of languages. Tendency can also be an implicational and non-implicational one, depends on whether it is conditioned or not. These are the different kinds of universals found across the languages. These universals statements are the representatives of the possibilities and impossibilities across the languages. Thus the language universals are the result of the cross linguistic comparison and are not the inferences drawn from a single language.

Vowels system

In phonetics according to Lass (1984), Vowels are sounds in spoken language, having two vied explanations. In the more general phonetic definition, vowel sound is produced with a wide open vocal tract, in a fashion that the tongue must not touch the other vocal organs in vocal tract, it means lips, teeth, or roof of the mouth. The other, phonological explanation is that, a vowel is a syllabic sound, the sound that creates the peak of a syllable. Semi vowels are phonetically similar to vowels but they do not form the syllable that is why they are called semi-vowels. In verbal languages as Lass (1984) explains that, phonemic vowels always make the peak (nucleus) in approximately all syllables, but the consonant sounds usually form the onset and codas in languages where they have onsets and codas, but there are other languages in the world that allow other sounds to form the peak (nucleus) of the syllable, for example in English l sound in word table ['tʰeɪb.l] when the speakers drop the weak vowel in the last syllable for example ['tʰeɪb.əl], or the syllabic r in

the Serbo-Croatian word vrt [vr̩t] "garden" is also a good example of semi vowels form the nucleus of the syllable.

In Latin the word vocalis, means "vocal" ("something which is verbal or related to voice") and in English it is Vowel. The term is commonly used in English as the vowel phonemes and there are five alphabets that represent more than twenty vowels in English. According to Lass (1984), the vowel system is the system of vowel phonemes, vowels, or vowel indexes in a single or multiple related languages. This subject exemplifies a number of different possible vowel systems in different languages of the world. The symbols used to represent vowels in different language are not necessarily indicates the actual pronunciation of the vowel sounds but present the patterns of different systems in target languages.

Lass (1984) further explain that, the vowel systems are made up from a different number of vowel attributes. All the vowel systems have leastwise two **fronting** and two **height** contrasts in their articulation. Other contrasts are developed from different **length** (also called **lax/tense**), **nasal**, and **lip rounding** characteristics of vowel sounds. In addition to above mentioned systems there are less common features that defines vowels systems also exist but not necessary to mention here. In the following examples only monophthongs are examined since the diphthongs are very difficult to categorize in terms of their place of articulation (because of a separate place of articulation for each targeted vowel sound). The following example have been extracted from Lass, (1984, p139-146).

THE SYSTEMS OF HIGH-LOW VOWELS

In most world languages commonly in token vowel systems there are three vowel phonemes: one front high, one high back and one low vowel without contrast in length.

Aleut

i u
 e

It means, in far corners of vowel space there is maximum dispersal of vowel quality.

Moroccan Arabic

i u
 a

Contrast in Length

There are some languages with the basic system of short vowels with their length counter parts in the language.

Alaskan Eskimo

i	u		i:	u:
	e			a:

THE SYSTEMS OF HIGH-MID-LOW VOWELS

No Contrast in Length

Ainu

i
 ε
 a

Yiddish

u
 o
 a

Contrast in Length

Hawaiin

i	u		i:	u:
ε	o		ɜ:	o:
	a			a:

Australian English

i:	ɜ:	o:		ɪ	ʊ
	ɜ:			e	ɔ
	ɜ:			æ	a

According to above mentioned examples it is noted that, according to this table for Australian-English does not mean that there are intermediate levels between different vowel positions, it means middle

and either high or low. The intermediate vowel positions for /o:/ and /ɔ/ merely show doubt about whether to make /o:/ mid or high and whether to make /ɔ/ mid or low.

Contrast in Nasality and Length

Beembe

i	u	i:	u:	ĩ	ũ
ɛ	o	ɛ:	o:	ẽ	õ
	a		a:		ã

Contrast in Rounding

Chuvash

i	y	ɯ	u
ɛ			
			ɔ

THE FOUR CONTRASTS IN HEIGHT

Contrast in Nasality and Rounding

French

i	y	u			
e	ø	o			
ɛ	œ	ɔ	ẽ	õ	õ̃
a		ɔ̃			õ̃

The maximum limit for vowel phonemes is about 21 monophthongs, for example in Swiss German and Alsatian German there are maximum vowels phonemes with length and rounding contrasts.

Literature review

Croft (1989) explains that in various world languages there would be many different kind of vowel sets: for example English has rich vowels in its phonemic inventory that other world languages do not have and the other way around. There are different variables are possible in world languages, such as nasalization of some vowels, Pharyngealisation or lengthening are other variant factors. In Ladefoged and Maddieson (1996) they found that there are five different possibilities of tongue height, three different possible

tongue position, and three different degrees of lip rounding feature in a single human verbal language, but, these combinations do not possible in a single human language. Maddieson, (1984); Maddieson & Precoda, (1990) with the data of 451 different languages in the UCLA Phonological Segment Inventory Database and in the UPSID concluded that, “the languages with the most distinctions in basic vowel lumber are German and Norwegian, both these languages with fifteen different vowel lumbers (in is worth mentioning that both these languages has a length contrast in their vowel system). Like de Bore (1999) demonstrated that, the Homo-Sapiens are capable of articulate and understand variety of vowels in principal. Research on different language across the globe indicates that most vowel

system in human languages are very regular and also can be predicted according to their sister languages. According to the research it is concluded that most consisting vowel system occurs in most languages is the five vowel system of /i/, /e/, /a/, /o/ and /u/. In general, there are certain vowel phonemes that occur much more frequently than other vowel phonemes. Those vowel phones are /i/, /a/ and /u/ which are part of the phonemic inventory of almost all languages it means 8296 languages about 87% of total existing spoken languages. The vowel in English word "but" also called **Shewa** is very rare in other languages and its occurring rate is less than 2%. It is also a general tendency in world languages that peripheral vowels are more frequent in language as compare to non-peripheral vowel phonemes.

All the languages with three vowel systems tend to have these vowels /i/, /a/ and /u/ in their phonemic inventory (Croft 1989). In four vowel systems the inventory has /ε/ or /i/ with the addition according to (de Bore 1999) and /ɔ/ (Croft 1989).

The Universals of vowel systems was pioneered by Glotin in (Glotin, 1995; Glotin & Laboissihe, 1996), they analyzed the system of vowels with the help of computer models of population. According to Glotin (1995), "first of all sat an input of a population of representatives that each should start with a repertoire of a fixed number of randomly taken vowel phonemes with both should be represented by acoustics and articulations. All these taken agents would act together in duals. The process begins with one that picks a vowel from its range and the other moves the vowel it heard to their closest vowel while moving the other vowel around. The time taken to move the vowels for each agent should be calculated accordingly. So the less time taken by the agent must the best fit the agents that considered the fittest are allowed to create more off springs from their parent vowel systems. According to Glotin small number of agents can develop a more realistic and coherent vowel system for the language under investigation, but sometimes represented by the agents are unable to develop a coherent system of vowels.

Data Analysis

Discussion on Language Universals

Comparing the inventories of fifteen Pakistani languages we find that all these fifteen languages have

an unrounded high front vowel /i/ or /i:/, a low vowel /a/ and a rounded high back vowel /u/ or /u:. In languages that have nine vowels system they have a close mid front and back vowel in their inventory. Like /e/ and /o/. Languages contain ten vowels usually a low front vowel /ε/ and back unrounded vowel/ ʌ /. Languages more than ten vowels in their inventories usually have long unrounded high front vowel /i:/, long low /a:/ and long high and mid back vowels like /u:/ and /o:/. It seems that no languages have long vowels without their short counterparts. Most languages have more than five vowels and less than thirteen vowels in their phonemic inventories. Languages have nine or more than nine vowels have at least one long vowel in their phonemic inventory.

Feature hierarchy

Short Vowels

Long Vowels.

This feature hierarchy shows that having short vowels is most unmarked feature in all these languages. As hierarchy moves towards right long vowels get add to the inventory. So it can be stated that having long vowels in the inventory is marked feature and it is the most uncommon feature of these languages.

Small Vowel Inventory Large vowel Inventory.

This feature hierarchy shows that having less number of vowels in phonemic inventory is most common feature most of these languages have greater number of vowels from five and less than ten vowels. So it can be stated that having large vowel inventory is most marked feature and very uncommon in these languages.

Conclusion

In a nut shell it is concluded after studying fifteen languages that all investigated languages have an unrounded high front vowel, a low vowel and rounded high back or unrounded vowel phoneme in their phonemic stock. Besides, all these languages with a five-vowel system include an unrounded mid-front vowel. Moreover, all languages with systems of vowel five or more in their inventory generally have a rounded mid-back vowel phoneme.

The languages with ten vowels usually a low front vowel /ε/ and back unrounded vowel/ ʌ /. Languages more than ten vowels in their inventories usually have long unrounded high front vowel /i:/,

long low /a:/ and long high and mid back vowels like /u:/ and /o:/. Languages have nine or more than nine vowels have at least one long vowel in their phonemic inventory. Thus, the findings showed the universal connection among these languages.

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